

DYMAN

**DYNAMICALLY MANAGED
SELF-COOLING HPC DATA
CENTERS**

<https://dyman-project.eu/>

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Commission
Horizon Europe Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101161930

DYMAN is a three-year EIC Pathfinder Challenges project that brings together 11 partners from five countries (Spain, Germany, Italy, Belgium and Turkey).

This diversity, in terms of organisation types and geographic location, ensures that the project results will reach different communities and countries and can contribute with complementary views and approaches.

DYMAN targets the development of a completely new design of adsorption chillers based on the following innovations: (1) New low-temperature adsorbents achieving high capacities at very low driving temperatures below 50 °C. (2) New type of adsorption heat exchangers made of 3D printed structures integrating the adsorption material into a porous structure, which reduces the internal thermal resistances and improvement of heat transfer by two-phase flow, enhancing the heat transfer rate and reducing the internal electricity consumption of the unit. Additionally, the project aims to develop a second core concept to further develop an existing two-phase cooling system, for high-performance computing servers to handle thermal loads more efficiently from next-generation processors. Goals include increasing cooling capacities for processors generating high heat fluxes like the Nvidia H100 chip which produces 70 W/cm². An additional objective is to recover 50% of waste heat from processors to generate additional cooling power through a sorption heat pump. Combining two-phase cooling directly with heat-powered cooling could significantly improve efficiency over conventional air or water-based cooling methods alone. The objective here is to: 1) further develop the present two-phase cooling system to work in an efficient way in combination with the sorption heat pump (concept 1). 2) Development of new evaporator with new advanced surfaces for high heat transfer coefficients. (3) Development of new condenser integrated with the heat adsorber of sorption heat pump.

This is a crucial component that can improve the efficiency of the whole integrated system to recovery up to 50% of rejected heat. Furthermore, the cooling data centre management is a complex engineering system with interactions with different components of the data centres. So, DYMAN proposes a new way of active management of the data centre integrating the cooling system as part of the optimization of processor management.

Interoperability and Ontology-based approach for Smart HPC systems

DYMAN will develop pioneering solutions to reduce the impact of thermal energy management in HCP installations and data server rooms. These solutions will be tested on a virtual commissioning level and a short-term physical test in two HPC facilities: the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (Barcelona, Spain) and the University of Torino (Torino, Italy).

Barcelona Supercomputing Center

- Location: Barcelona, Spain
- Partners involved: BSC, EAS, IDP, BDTA, SOR
- DYMAN use cases applications: Cooling of a central or in-row system

University of Torino

- Location: Torino, Italy
- Partners involved: UNITO, BDTA, SOR, IQ
- DYMAN use cases applications: Cooling of a rack-integrated system

The inefficiency of standard adsorption chillers and water network complexities hindered achieving the desired energy efficiency. As data centres' cooling demand continues to rise, alternative solutions are needed:

- 1** For large HPC super computers with processors and storages in different racks: In-Row Solution: Water cooled compute racks drive the adsorption chiller, which generates chilled water for the separate storage racks.
- 2** For small data centres or individual racks where processors and air-cooled components are within the same rack. Rack-integrated solution: The adsorption chillers are integrated into the rear door of the rack and are directly driven by a two-phase flow system cooling the processors and will directly provide air-cooling with an attached fan coil.

So as first core concept, DYMAN targets the development of a completely new design of adsorption chillers based on the following innovations: (1) New low-temperature adsorbents achieving high capacities at very low driving temperatures below 50 °C. (2) New type of adsorption heat exchangers made of 3D printed structures integrating the adsorption material into a porous structure, which reduces the internal thermal resistances and improvement of heat transfer by two-phase flow, enhancing the heat transfer rate and reducing the internal electricity consumption of the unit.

Innovations

- ✓ Low-temperature adsorbents that achieve high capacities at very low conduction temperatures below 50 °C.
- ✓ New adsorption heat exchangers made with 3D printed structures that integrate the adsorption material into a porous structure, reducing the internal thermal resistance.
- ✓ Two-phase cooling for high-performance computing servers to handle thermal loads more efficiently from next-generation processors.
- ✓ A new type of adsorption cooling system integration in the data centre environment.
- ✓ A new form of active data centre management integrating the cooling system as part of the optimisation of processor management by providing an ontology based on an AI-assisted approach to O&M practices.

DYMAN

DYNAMICALLY MANAGED SELF-COOLING
HPC DATA CENTERS

<https://dyman-project.eu/>

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Commission
Horizon Europe Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101161930